

LOCAL STRAIN CONCENTRATIONS IN A REINFORCED MICROVASCULAR NETWORK

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SUMMARY

Strain concentrations associated with the presence of a microvascular network in a polymer matrix are measured using fluorescent digital image correlation (FDIC). The accuracy of the measurement technique is established for a specimen containing only a single microchannel. The influence of localized micro- and nano- particle reinforcement around the channel is also investigated using this simplified geometry. Three-dimensional network specimens with different structural designs were fabricated and loaded in uniaxial tension. The resulting strain concentrations are compared as a function of channel spacing and location. The results provide insight into the mechanical behavior of microvascular networks and demonstrate the utility of FDIC as a characterization tool at these length scales.

Keywords: digital image correlation, microvascular, nanoscale reinforcement

INTRODUCTION

Advances in direct-write assembly methods have enabled the creation of synthetic materials with complex embedded microvascular networks that emulate many of the key responses of biological vascular systems. Toohey et al. have reported a self-healing coating/substrate design [1,2] that delivers healing agent to cracks in a coating via a three-dimensional microvascular network in the substrate. Williams et al. [3] have developed a vascularized composite sandwich structure that is capable of rebonding impact-induced delamination damage. The continuous delivery of healing components through a vascular network represents a significant advance over previously reported self-healing materials in which a finite supply of healing agent is stored in capsules or hollow fibers [4-6]. In contrast to these compartmentalized approaches, vascularized systems distribute healing agent throughout the material, such that any given part has access to the supply of the whole system. Recent analyses suggest ways to design and optimize these vascularized networks for healing and cooling with minimized impact on structural performance [7-10]. In order to realize these optimized structures, the mechanical integrity of the network must be characterized.

In the current work, we explore the effects of channel spacing and channel reinforcement on the local strain concentrations in a microvascular self-healing composite. Displacement and strain are measured by a fluorescent digital image correlation (FDIC) technique [11-13] in samples with a 0/90° stacking sequence between layers of microchannels. This geometry was implemented for the healing of cracks in brittle coatings by Toohey et al. [1]. The experimental technique is first verified on a finite strip with an isolated microchannel loaded in tension, for which an analytical solution exists. Measurements on fully three-dimensional networks reveal the influence of channel spacing on the mechanical behavior.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sample Preparation

Epoxy matrix samples containing microvascular networks were manufactured by direct-write fabrication described previously by Toohey et al. [1] and Therriault et al. [14]. A fugitive organic ink (60% microcrystalline wax, 40% petroleum jelly by weight) was deposited in a layer-by-layer manner with depositions placed at every location where a microchannel was desired in the final sample. The ink scaffold was then infiltrated with liquid epoxy and allowed to cure. The ink was subsequently removed by moderate heating (80°C) and applying vacuum to the microchannel outlets.

The resulting samples contained embedded microvascular networks of 200 μm diameter channels that were fully connected in three dimensions. The samples had a 0/90° stacking sequence between subsequent layers of channels, with connections from one layer to the next at the channel intersections. Figure 1 contains a representative image of a microvascular sample, with a micrograph inset revealing the microchannel cross-section. As detailed in Fig. 2 and Table 1, three different microvascular geometries (denoted I, II, III) were created for testing by varying the spacing between channels in the xy plane. Channel spacing in the yz plane was the same among all microvascular sample geometries. Small deviations in the relative position of microchannels on the order of a few microns were common due to imperfections in the manufacturing process.

Fig. 1. Images of (a) single channel samples with micrographs of both unreinforced (top) and reinforced (bottom) channels and (b) a representative microvascular network sample with a micrograph of channel layout. Scalebars are 250 μm .

Fig. 2. Schematic drawings for different microvascular network sample geometries (Table I).

Table I. Sample geometry dimensions.

Label Architecture	a (mm)	b (mm)	c(mm)
Type I Offset	2.0	0.7	2.0
Type II Offset	1.0	0.7	2.0
Type III Aligned	2.0	0.7	2.0

Strain Measurement

Fluorescent digital image correlation (FDIC) is a full-field technique for measuring strain and displacement [11]. As in digital image correlation, a correlation algorithm is applied to obtain kinematic information from digital images acquired during deformation. The correlation requires random surface features that deform with the specimen surface; in FDIC this pattern is created by applying fluorescent silica nanoparticles onto the region of interest. When using silica particles sized at approximately 100 nm, a displacement resolution of 20 nm has been achieved [11]. For the current investigation, particles on the order of 300 nm created an appropriate surface pattern for the optical setup and the feature size of interest. Particles containing the fluorescent dye rhodamine B were synthesized following the procedure described by Verhaegh et al. [15]. The optical system for acquisition of FDIC images consisted of a fluorescent microscope, an objective lens (20x magnification and 0.4 N.A.), and a CCD camera. With a pixel density of 1.88 pixels/ μm , this setup has a resolving power of 826 nm based on the Rayleigh criterion for self-luminescent objects.

Correlations were performed using an in-house DIC code in which a coarse-fine search is implemented to obtain an initial guess for a Newton-Raphson scheme [12]. Subset sizes were 31 by 31 pixels (16.5 μm), and correlations were performed every 10 pixels (5.3 μm). Correlation was not attempted anywhere inside the channel boundary, where the displacement becomes discontinuous. Accordingly, no displacement and strain data were obtained within a distance approximately the size of a subset around each channel. Strain was calculated by numerically differentiating the displacement measured by DIC, rather than using the displacement gradients obtained from the correlation directly. Displacement data were smoothed using a moving average that spanned one subset in each of the two in-plane dimensions before employing a finite-difference scheme for differentiation.

Samples were loaded in tension along the x axis (according to the coordinate system established in Fig. 3) using a miniature load frame while viewing the xy plane of the sample. The applied load was measured using a 100 lb capacity load cell. Samples were clamped tightly in flat-faced grips and loaded at a rate of $1 \mu\text{m/s}$. Deformation was paused at regular intervals to capture fluorescent images for correlation. Load data were used to calculate the far-field values of strain for normalization. The elastic modulus of the epoxy matrix varied between 3.2 and 3.5 GPa, depending on the time of testing. Dynamic mechanical analysis of the matrix material was performed to establish these values of modulus.

RESULTS

Single Channel Specimens

The experimentally determined displacement and strain fields in the loading x -direction around an isolated microchannel, $280 \mu\text{m}$ in diameter, under uniaxial tension are shown in Fig. 3. Contours are drawn at 50 nm intervals over a total range of displacement of $3.8 \mu\text{m}$. The contours of constant displacement, which without the presence of the channel would be vertically oriented and straight, curve into the channel. As expected, a strain concentration develops at the top ($+y$) and bottom ($-y$) of the microchannel, while the strain drops almost to zero on the left ($-x$) and right ($+x$) sides.

An analytical solution for a finite-width plate in uniaxial tension [16] is inset on the upper left corners of the contour plots in Figs. 3(a) and (b). Experimentally determined strain and displacement are in excellent agreement with this analytical solution. The normalized strain along a vertical line through the center of the channel is plotted in Fig. 4. This plot shows the maximum observed strain concentration was 1.9, while the value predicted by the analytical solution is 3.0. The spatial resolution of FDIC is approximately equal to the subset size used in the correlation; hence the technique effectively averages strain and displacement over the area covered by each subset. The strain concentration is greatest at the boundary of the channel, but correlations were not performed directly adjacent to this boundary.

Fig. 3. Experimentally determined (a) displacement and (b) strain fields in the vicinity of an isolated $280 \mu\text{m}$ diameter microchannel with analytical solution inset on upper left for comparison ($\epsilon_0 = 0.39\%$).

The stiffening effect of particle reinforcement locally placed around a single 200 μm diameter microchannel is evident from the normalized strain field in Fig. 5. The strain around a reinforced channel drops to values at or below the far-field strain in a shorter distance from the channel as compared with the case of the unreinforced channel in Fig. 4. Because the reinforced material surrounding the channel is stiffer than the matrix, there is a decrease in strain when approaching this region. The asymmetry of the strain concentration in this reinforced sample is due to the uneven distribution of the reinforcement around the channel. The ring of particle reinforcement was thinnest on the top (+y) side of the channel, where the strain concentration is highest (1.6).

Fig. 4. Normalized strain along a vertical line through the center of each corresponding microchannel.

Fig. 5. Experimentally determined strain field around an isolated 200 μm diameter reinforced channel.

Microvascular Network Specimens

The type I network geometry had the largest spacing between neighboring microchannels in the xy plane. The normalized strain field around a single microchannel in this type I geometry is similar to those surrounding a single, isolated microchannel. As shown in Fig. 4, the maximum normalized strain is slightly higher for this network sample (2.1) than for the single channel sample (1.9), and the strain concentration remains higher farther from the microchannel. The normalized strain along a line connecting the centers of these two microchannels is plotted in Fig. 6. For comparison, the analytical solution for a single, isolated channel is also plotted at each microchannel location. The strain around each of these two microchannels is comparable with that of the solution for an isolated channel, with the exception of the bottom half of the strain field ($-y$) where the strain in the network remains above the far-field value away from the microchannel. This region of elevated strain is associated with the microchannel that intersects the nearest subsurface channel.

In the type II microvascular geometry, the distance between microchannels in the x direction was closer than in a type I sample. As in the type I network, the maximum strain concentration in the type II network (2.3) occurs at the microchannel that is intersected by the nearest subsurface microchannel. Although the maximum strain concentration is about the same as in the type I sample, the closer x -direction spacing confines the region of elevated strain. This confining occurs because the strain must drop to a minimum at the left side of the neighboring microchannel over a shorter distance than in a type I sample. The strain plotted in Fig. 6 for a type II network reveals

a trend similar to that in the type I network. However, the strain in the type II network does not drop to the same minimum strain seen in the analytical solution far from the channel. Note that maximum strain concentration is not plotted in Fig. 6, because the maximum occurs off center from the two microchannels.

The type III microvascular geometry had neighboring microchannels that are in the closest proximity to one another, because there was no offset between subsequent layers in the y -direction. Because the y spacing was less in this geometry, the locations of maximum strain concentration (the tops and bottoms of microchannels) have the least separation in these samples. Consequently, the normalized strain field shows higher levels of strain concentration (up to 2.8) at locations farther from the microchannels than in the previous two network geometries. There are two line scans plotted in Fig. 6 for the type III geometry; one of them is a plot of the strain between the centers of the two channels ($x/r = 0$). The other is a plot of the strain along a vertical line through the region of maximum strain ($x/r = 0.4$). The strain along both of these vertical lines remains well above the level of strain far from the channels in all the previous geometries and in the analytical solution.

Fig. 6. Normalized strain along a line connecting the centers of two microchannels in each of the network geometries.

CONCLUSIONS

Measurements of the displacement field surrounding a single channel in tension were made and verified with an analytical solution. Excellent agreement was obtained between experimental and analytical displacement and strain fields, demonstrating the ability of fluorescent DIC to make accurate measurements of the mechanical response around a microchannel. Samples with a fully three-dimensional microvascular network had higher strain concentrations compared with that caused by a single, isolated microchannel. These higher strain concentrations are attributed to the influence of sub-surface microchannels, microchannel cross-sectional shape, and neighboring microchannels. Inter-channel spacing in the direction perpendicular to the loading direction had the largest impact on the magnitude of strain concentration. Localized particle reinforcement significantly altered the strain concentration around the microchannels. Overall, the measurement of strain fields using fluorescent digital image correlation should provide valuable insight into the design of microvascular networks, and aid in achieving effective self-healing while maintaining optimal structural performance.

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